

Analysis of Women's Struggle in Achieving Self-Existence in the Novel Sintren by Ery Agus

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Abstract

The purpose of the paper analysis is In men's culture, women cannot be themselves. Women do not get the opportunity to show their abilities and their existence. The problems faced by women to achieve self-existence and women's struggles in the novel Sintren by Dining Widya Yudhistira against patriarchy about women. The feminism theory of existentialism is used as a basis to answer the problem. This study shows that the problems faced by women in achieving self-existence are the very strong patriarchal tradition in people's lives, poverty, and the ambivalent nature that arises from women themselves.

Keywords: *struggles, woman, self-existence, femininity*

INTRODUCTION

In this Sintren novel, it is investigated using feminist theory because the spirit of women to show their existence is very strong. Since childhood, Saraswati's character has been identified as a woman who is different from other women in her village. Her strong desire to continue her education to a higher level is described as having to face very formidable challenges and obstacles as a "different" female figure in breaking the domination and myths about the female figure. In addition, the feminist spirit is very strong, represented by the character Saraswati, who is always described as a person who fights against traditions and construction establishments in her social environment. Literary works are a reflection of social life which shows a correlation between literary works and social phenomena that occur around humans.

Women must fight for themselves to be able to show their existence in the public sphere. This is because the cultural construction created and strengthened by the patriarchy through myths and stereotypes about women causes women to become weak and subordinated parties. states that the myths about women constructed by the patriarchal cause women to become subordinated and become the other. This impropriety can be seen from the dichotomy of a division of roles. The dichotomy of gender roles causes gender problems. This causes the opportunities given to women to develop their potential and competence to be more limited when compared to the opportunities given to men.

METHOD

This study of analysis uses a descriptive qualitative method because it explains a social event for how the writer us for analyzing the paper. This method is seen by the writer to be very important because this method will show a form of explanation related to a phenomenon that is interpreted in the context and concept of writing. Of course, in carrying out this research, the author uses a hermeneutic approach because this paper analysis will be studied by exegesis of the contents and adjusting to the events that occurred at that time. The method used in this research is the descriptive method. Through this research, the researcher describes the struggle of women to show their existentialism which is represented in the novel Sintren by Dining Widya Yudistira. The description of the findings is based on the results of the analysis of the data. The primary data in this paper is a novel entitled Sintren by Dining Widya Yudistira. The existentialist feminist theory is the basis for analyzing the data.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

The findings in this study are Many obstacles must be faced by women in their struggle to equalize their existence and equal rights with men. One of these obstacles is the traditions or customs that apply in the life of the social community. Traditions or customs will be very interesting if the conversation is associated with women and the feminist movement.

Women become the second class and do not have the freedom to do activities in the public sphere. the traditions created by the patriarchy have a very significant role in the slow development of

the feminist movement. This tradition prevents women from self-existence who still adhere to the construction of patriarchal culture.

The purpose of this analysis of papers in the form of discussions is an action of inhibition and restriction to have a more advanced thought, develop a mindset, and equalize the rights of women with men. Restrictions on opportunities for higher education make women stupid. Women occupy positions that are given and protected by men so that the construction of patriarchal culture will be stronger and stronger.

Through this construction, men make women's positions lower than that of men. In the novel *Sintren*, several attempts are made by female characters to show their existence so that their existence and position get recognition from men so that women are no longer the other.

CONCLUSION

For how the writer subjectively sees from the paper analysis that The struggle of the female characters in the novel *Sintren*. is a struggle to get the opportunity to achieve higher education, to free oneself from all things that hinder his struggle. Women have to struggle to get the desired social roles.

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